

RIVEAL PROJECT

RIPARIAN FOREST VALUES AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES – RIVER REGULATION EFFECTS IN RIPARIAN CARBON STOCK

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RIPARIAN CARBON VARIATION

Carbon stocks from riparian forests and fluvial landscapes have potentially a great contribution to the total carbon pools of Mediterranean systems. However, it depends on multiple effects of human disturbance, such as land-use and land-cover change (LULC), climate change, damming and local and regional abiotic factors. In addition, it differs with species composition, age of individuals, stem density and vegetation development, amongst other factors, such as management of riparian zones and diseases of trees.

FREE-FLOWING RIVERS

Average C storage (above and belowground) of mature riparian forests of Ribeira de Alcolobre ranged from 122.4 to 201.2 tC ha⁻¹, depending on the dominant species, stem density, vegetation development and successional stage of the different stands.

In relation to species, *Acacia dealbata* showed the highest average carbon stock per unit area (251 ± 90 tC ha⁻¹) followed by *Alnus glutinosa* (162 ± 12 tC ha⁻¹) and by *Salix salviifolia* (73 ± 17 tC ha⁻¹). The woody tree compartment contributed with 79%, followed by the understory vegetation (12%) and lastly by the soil mineral layer (9%) (Fernandes *et al.* *Forests* 2020, 11, 376; doi:10.3390/f111040376).

C STORAGE CHANGE DOWNSTREAM OF DAMS

To understand the C storage differences between dammed rivers, we followed a temporal comparison using two case studies and referential data.

We collected:

- remote sensing pre-dam (1965) and post-dam (2013) data from River Lima, downstream Touvedo, a run-of-river dam, and River Alva, downstream Fronhas, a storage reservoir (more details in Aguiar *et al.* *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 2016; doi:10.1016/j.landurbplan.2016.04.009);
- field data (spring 2019) on riparian species composition and cover;
- literature data on carbon stock reference values of the mapped LULC classes.

Map of the LULC and riparian patches in a section of River Alva. LULC buffer is the area submerged by centenary floods.

CARBON REFERENTIAL (tC ha⁻¹)

Highest values of Carbon storage: Riparian tree class, followed by the Unmanaged Forest and Managed Forest.

Carbon referential for the LULC in the riparian zone (from literature) and riparian woody species and riparian herbs (from field data). *derived from Fernandes et al., 2020, 11, 376; doi:10.3390/f11040376 and field work.

TOTAL CARBON STORAGE CHANGES

- ▶ Overall increase of the total carbon stocks (all components) after hydrological regulation, in both case studies.
- ▶ High variability of Carbon storage along both rivers.
- ▶ River Alva impaired by Fronhas – storage reservoir had a higher increase in the total carbon storage, from 1.79Mt C (pre-dam) to 4.74Mt C (post-dam) than River Lima impaired by Touvedo, run-of-river dam, which increased from 2.85 Mt C in the pre-dam to 4.56 Mt C after hydrological regulation.

Carbon storage (tons of Carbon) variation downstream from the dam in River Alva (left graph) and River Lima (right graph) pre-dam (1965) and post-dam (2013) fluvial landscapes. Sampling units (SU) are 250-m long river stretches numbered along the river from the dam to downstream.

CARBON CHANGES OF RIPARIAN WOODS AND LULC (tC ha⁻¹)

High variability of Carbon from Riparian patches and LULC along the river in both case studies and dates.

Carbon storage variation along River Lima (panels above) and River Alva (panels below) of pre-dam (1965) and post-dam (2013) for Riparian tree class (left panels) and LULC (right panels). SU=sampling units.

- ▶ River Lima (impaired by a run-of-river dam)
 - Expansion of riparian vegetation towards the floodplain resulting, in part, from the agricultural land abandonment in river margins.
- ▶ River Alva (impaired by a storage reservoir)
 - Marked riparian expansion in the post-dam period;
 - Vegetation encroachment towards the active channel;
 - Increase of Managed forests in the post-dam period, mostly eucalyptus plantations.

CONCLUSIONS

- ▶ Riparian carbon storage increased after hydrological regulation and have high variability along the river.
- ▶ The different hydrological disturbances, imposed by the distinct dam operation schemes, led to distinct contributions to carbon stocks changes in riverine areas.
- ▶ Differences in carbon stocks between case studies are related to changes in the species composition and the total cover of the LULC classes.

